

RADx-UP REVISED Project Photo Submission Guidelines

(Revised January 2023)

The Coordination and Data Collection Center (CDCC) is collecting photographs and to show the impact of COVID-19 and RADx-UP testing projects on diverse communities across the U.S. **We invite you to share original photographs of the people, places, and things that tell your community's COVID-19 story.**

Why are we collecting photos?

Photographs can have a powerful effect on how people understand the world. We want to see the impact of COVID-19 through your community's eyes and highlight the diversity of experiences and perspectives across RADx-UP projects.

How will my photos be used?

Submitted photos will be added to an image bank, or repository, that will be accessible to all members of the RADx-UP community. RADx-UP projects will be able to use images from the image bank for promotional (Ex: professional journals, manuscripts, recruitment flyers, newspaper articles, etc.) community engagement purposes (open houses, meetings, annual reports, volunteer events, etc). Photos will also be displayed in a secure folder for RADx-UP only use and viewing. All are prohibited from repurposing or selling any photos for monetary gain.

What are some themes to consider when taking photos?

This is an opportunity to get creative and share what you'd like people to know about your community's response to COVID-19. Possible themes to consider include:

- At-home COVID-19 testing
- Mental health and wellness
- Mutual aid (eg, food distribution, diaper drives)
- Human connections during COVID-19
- Family life
- Going virtual for work and school

In order to protect the privacy of individuals receiving health care, we will **NOT** accept photos taken at clinical sites, including health centers, hospitals, mobile or pop-up testing and/or vaccination sites, or other locations where patients receive health care. However, photos can be staged with community members who agree, or consent, to act out that they are receiving health services such as testing and vaccination.

In addition to protecting privacy of individuals receiving healthcare, please also consider other aspects of privacy, such as obscuring addresses where people may live or receive services, name tags, and other identifying objects.

We will NOT publicly share the names of the research studies or name the population being photographed. While we want to visually represent diverse communities we do not want to create any stress for individuals who could be identified by the community name or study—for example, in populations of people who are undocumented, who are surviving cancer, who inject drugs, who are experiencing homelessness, or are otherwise likely to want their right to privacy respected.

What information do I need to submit with my photos?

Please provide the name and email address of the person submitting the photo, location (city, state) where each photo was taken, date the photo was taken, and a brief caption describing the people, places, activities, or things depicted. Accompanying stories are encouraged but not required.

Submission Guidelines

- 1) All photos must be original work. No third party may own or control any materials the photo contains, and the photo must not infringe upon the trademark, copyright, moral rights, intellectual rights, or rights of privacy of any entity or person.
- 2) Consent forms must be signed and submitted for each person who appears in photos. People under the age of 18 appearing in photos must have signed parent or guardian consent. (See consent forms for details).
- 3) Photos must be submitted via the portal on myRADxUPhome
- 4) RADx-UP reserves the right to reject any entry that is deemed inappropriate or does not conform to stated guidelines.
- 5) By entering photo(s), you agree that submitted photos can be used by the CDCC and other RADx-UP funded projects for promotional or community engagement purposes. (see above for examples.)